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Review Article

**STUDYING NURSES' SATISFACTION WITH THE HEALTH
SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT PLAN AT IRANIAN UNIVERSITIES
OF MEDICAL SCIENCES: A REVIEW****Abdolreza Gilavand**Social Determinants of Health Research Center, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical
Sciences, Ahvaz, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: The most important guarantor of the success of the health system development plan is the attention paid to health services providers, including nurses. Studying satisfaction can help designers and its implementing agents to better understand its strengths and weaknesses and improve it. Therefore, this research was conducted to evaluate the satisfaction of nurses from the health system development plan in hospitals and treatment educational centers affiliated to Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences.

Materials and Methods: This is a simple overview conducted in 2018. Research data has been collected through the search of published articles in Internet resources and scientific databases, and through the searching three terms "health system development plan, nurses and satisfaction" without any limitation of language and time.

Findings: This research showed that many nurses are not satisfied with the implementation of the health development plan in Iran. Of course, in some cases, the satisfaction was moderate. However, in a recent review research, based on patients' opinions, it has been shown that the plan has been able to satisfy patients.

Discussion and Conclusion: Considering the novelty of the plan and extension of its dimensions, and in order to reduce nurses' dissatisfaction in cases such as increase in the number of clients, the number of watches and inappropriate accommodation facilities, it is suggested that some working procedures such as the establishment of an integrated distribution system for patients, employment, maintenance and returning specialist forces and allocating appropriate space as nurses' pavilion.

Keywords: *Health System Development Plan, Satisfaction, Nurses, Iran.*

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INTRODUCTION:

In today's world, the health promotion team plays a key role in improving disease prevention and treatment. Especially when health system managers understand the importance of the Health Promotion Team and plan it decisively to succeed. Nurses usually play the role of coordinating the team, often as managers and skilled people they can actively influence decision-making. Experience has shown that if the nurse does not play an active role as a member or coordinator of the team, the health promotion team will not continue, or will continue to work only formally and without regard to health and irregularly. Nurses, on the other hand, do not usually have a motivation to engage in activities and take effective responsibility because of heavy workload in hospitals and lack of adequate support, lack of job security, low salaries, high work hours. However, the educated managers, in the prevention (prevention, treatment and rehabilitation) dimension, they also have clinical experience; in patients' mortality, hospital infections, the complaints and dissatisfaction are susceptible, and to their indicators also was paid attention. Nurses can also actively participate in a team of one or more nurses, specialist physicians, radiologists, laboratories, pharmacists, etc., and provide comprehensive reports on patient care system and health promotion phases.

In the successful implementation of any plan or program in the field of health, the role of manpower is undeniable, because human resources are the most important factor of the effectiveness and efficiency of each organization (1). Because of the key role of nurses in caring for patients, paying attention to their morale and their motivation in form of studying satisfaction is a high priority, because it affects directly the health of patients, the amount of leave, creativity, positive performance, and collaboration with organization's plans (2). Also, high workload, long working hours, patient death, unpredictable nature of occupation, inadequate preparation, lack of psychological support, confrontation with doctors, ambiguity in options, and increase of rules and regulations are some factors affecting the reduction of nurses' satisfaction (3). Failure to pay attention to this problem disrupts the organization's system in the long run and reduces the sense of responsibility, abnormal behaviors, and abandonment (4-5). In early 2014, in Iran, the Health System Development Plan was implemented in the following seven service packages: Reduced hospitalization rates, support for doctors staying in deprived areas, the presence of specialized physicians residing in government hospitals over 64 beds, improving hotel accommodation in government hospitals, improving the quality of visit services in government hospitals,

the program for the promotion of normal delivery, financial protection program (6). In the end of 2017, Gilavand et al conducted a review research entitled "Assessment of the Health System Development Plan in Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences for the Empowerment of the Society" and showed that the health system development plan has been able to do its first and most important goal, namely reducing successfully the payment from the pocket of patients. Ultimately, it achieves the satisfaction and empowerment of the society in this regard (7). The most important guarantor of the success of the health system development plan is the attention paid to health care providers, including nurses. Satisfaction survey can help designers and their implementing agents to better understand and improve their strengths and weaknesses. Therefore, this research was carried out to determine the satisfaction of nurses about the health system development plan in hospitals and educational treatment centers affiliated to Iranian universities of medical sciences.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was conducted as a simple overview in 2018 to assess nurses' satisfaction with health system development plan in hospitals and educational centers affiliated to Iranian Universities of Medical Sciences. Research data has been collected through the search of published articles in Internet resources and scientific databases including (SID, MAGIRAN, PubMed, Scopus and Web of Science) and with searching 3 terms of "health system development plan, nurses and satisfaction" without linguistic and time restrictions. In the initial search, 15 related researches were found, among which 6 researches completely related were used in this research.

FINDINGS:

Several studies have been conducted in Iran on the satisfaction of nurses about the health system development plan. Here are 6 examples:

Bahmanziari et al carried out a study to determine the level of nurses' satisfaction with the implementation of health system development in educational hospitals of Shiraz. This study was conducted on nurses of 13 educational hospitals in Shiraz in March 2014. Of the 3,100 nurses, 342 nurses were selected using the Cochran formula and stratified sampling method. The research tool was a questionnaire adopted from Nurses' Survey Questionnaire of the National Institute for Health Researches, which included two sections of demographic information and satisfaction questions. The results of this research showed that 68.9% of nurses were dissatisfied with the implementation of the plan, and 29.2% of the respondents were satisfied. The most satisfaction was

from training details (43.3%) and the most dissatisfaction with the number of clients (71.2%). 68.5% of nurses were dissatisfied with work place accommodation facilities after the implementation of the plan, and there was a significant correlation between age and satisfaction. In this research, the amount of nurses' dissatisfaction was reported to be high in cases such as an increase in the number of clients, the number of watches and unsatisfactory accommodation facilities (8).

Ghorbannia et al conducted a research aimed at determining the job satisfaction of nurses from the health system development plan at Pasteur Hospital in Bam in 2016. The population under study was 195 nurses from Pasteur Hospital in Bam. Sampling was done by census method. Data were collected using a Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire of nurses working in hospitals affiliated to the Ministry of Health. The results showed that the highest level of nursing staff satisfaction was related to the given teachings of Health System Development Plan (42.1% relatively satisfied) and the least satisfaction related to the increase in the number of clients (64.1% completely dissatisfied). Also, the results of ANOVA test showed that there was a significant relationship between the number of clients, the quality of diagnostic activities, the treatment of suggestions and requests, satisfaction with the treatment of patients and attendants, the teachings provided and the facilities at the workplace. In this research, many nurses were not satisfied with the implementation of the development plan (9).

Nakhaei et al conducted a research to determine the satisfaction of nurses about the health system development plan in hospitals affiliated to Birjand University of Medical Sciences. This study was conducted on 380 nurses working in two hospitals affiliated to Birjand University of Medical Sciences in 2017. Data were collected using a demographic questionnaire and a Job Satisfaction Questionnaire of Job Descriptive Index (JDI) based on Likert scale. The results showed that the average satisfaction of nurses with a majority of 75.4% was moderate. The lowest satisfaction was related to working conditions (4.9%) and salaries and benefits (0.2%) and the highest satisfaction was in the field of the direct responsible and collaborator (49.7%). The relation of satisfaction with age was statistically significant, so that satisfaction in nurses over 40 years old was more than other age groups. The satisfaction of nurses was not satisfactory in this research (10).

Shariati et al carried out a study was conducted to evaluate the satisfaction of nurses, patients and

companions with the implementation of the health system development plan in Ahvaz hospitals in 2016. The research population consisted of 300 nurses, 300 patients and 300 patients' attendants from Ahvaz educational hospitals. Sampling was done randomly. The research tool was a researcher-constructed questionnaire. The method of scoring was three-option Lickert (complete satisfaction, moderate satisfaction and dissatisfied with the implementation of the development plan). The results showed that the average score of satisfaction with health development plan was 30.64 ± 6.42 in nurses. 83.1% were dissatisfied, 16.4% had a moderate satisfaction and 0.5% were completely satisfied. In this research, most nurses were dissatisfied with the implementation of the health system development plan (11).

Shahraki et al conducted a research with the aim of evaluating the viewpoints of staff working in government hospitals of Mashhad about the effects of implementation of the health system development plan on the quality of health services provided to patients and the professional conditions of the staff. This study was conducted in 2016 with a survey among the medical and administrative staff occupying in two public hospitals in Mashhad. The survey form, in addition to the personal and employment details of participants, contained two questions as an open response, in which respondents should comment on the advantages and disadvantages of the plan. Respondents were able to answer at last three cases in the answer to each question. The results showed that 109 people participated in this survey. Of the job position, 30.3% of the participants were nurses and 50.4% of the participants were physicians. The most beneficial effects of the plan from the participants' point of view were as follows: three subjects of "Social justice, insurance coverage and patient costs reduction" (59.6%), "increased satisfaction of health care" (27.5%), "increased incomes of doctors and Hospital employed staff" (24.8%). The most common disadvantages of the plan were, from perspective of respondents, the followings: "increase in the number of patient/hospital disturbance (59.6%), the disproportionate size of patients with the number of medical personnel and consequently an increase in the workload of the medical staff" (49.5%), and "lack of adequate infrastructure before implementation of the plan and, consequently, non-fit of physical facilities at run-time" (31.2%). (12).

The results of the study of Kalhor et al regarding job satisfaction of health staff after implementation of the health system development plan in Kowsar Hospital in Qazvin showed that the highest and lowest job

satisfaction of nurses in relation to personal life was 80.2% and the workflow area of the hospital was 96.4%. In total, 78.2% of nurses had a moderate level of job satisfaction (13).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

This research showed that many nurses are not satisfied with the implementation of the health development plan in Iran. Of course, in some cases, satisfaction was moderate. Meanwhile, in a review research recently conducted under the title "Assessing the Health System Development Plan in Iranian Universities Medical Sciences in terms of society empowerment", it became clear that the health system development plan has been able to achieve its primary and most important goal, namely reducing Successfully payment from the pocket of the patients. Ultimately, it achieved the satisfaction and empowerment of the individuals in this regard (7). The health system development plan is aimed at serving more and more patients, while in this project, there is always more pressure on nurses and the expectations of families for improving their patients. The nursing staff has not still changed, and in this regard, some hospitals are far from the global standards.

The implementation of this plan has made more apparent the shortage of manpower, especially in the nursing sector with which treatment centers have already confronted. Regarding the novelty of the plan and the extension of its dimensions, it is necessary for managers of organizations to improve productivity and the delivery of services, since nurses are known as one of the main circles of patients' treatment and their satisfaction plays an important role in advancing the goals of the plan of the development of the health system and, more importantly, the satisfaction of the patients from the treatment process.

Regarding the results of the study and in order to reduce the amount of nurses' dissatisfaction, in some cases such as increasing the number of clients, the number of watches and inappropriate accommodation facilities, it is recommended that the authorities and related organizations try to resolve the challenge and the problem of nursing dissatisfaction by selecting the appropriate strategies in areas like the establishment of a regular and integrated system of distribution of patients between treatment centers, recruitment, employment and returning of specialist forces, promotion of societal culture in order to shape reasonable expectations from nurses in performing tasks, determining the workload balanced with diversity and flexibility for each nurse, allocating a given space with sufficient facilities as nurses' pavilion.

One of the limitations of this research is that so far no extensive studies have been carried out on the satisfaction of nurses about the implementation of the Health Development Plan in Iran. Therefore, only 6 cases in this research have been investigated and their results may not be generalized to the whole country.

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